
Analysis and Development of a Modular Fault-Tolerant Multistring Power Converter for Solar Photovoltaic Applications

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Keywords: Power Converter, Photovoltaic, Multistring Inverter, Fault tolerant, Reliability, Modular

Due to the ongoing growth of solar photovoltaic (PV) generation, PV systems scalability, reliability, and cost reduction are of major interest. This paper proposes a modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter to address this challenge. The proposed inverter features a modular dc-dc conversion stage and a dc-ac conversion stage. This configuration allows scaling the inverter power rating by simply increasing the number of PV strings and associated dc-dc modules and adapting the second-stage heat-extraction and filtering capabilities. The fault-tolerant capability allows for surviving a first semiconductor device fault on either stage and continue operation. This property allows almost doubling the inverter lifetime compared to non-fault-tolerant solutions (dismissing inverter reparation and degraded mode of operation), with a low impact on the cost increase (3 % to 7 %) and an efficiency reduction of only 0.5 % after a fault occurs. A generalized reliability assessment demonstrates that lifetime increase is achieved regardless of the number of modules. More so, it allows reducing the operation and maintenance costs and revenue losses due to unscheduled system shutdowns. In order to validate the proposed inverter, a lab-scale prototype with two modules has been

tested under emulated faults, validating the feasibility of the proposed inverter.

1 Introduction

In the last years, solar photovoltaic (PV) generation is continuously growing on the energy share and it is expected to be up to 8500 GW worldwide.^[1] In order to achieve this, further cost reductions are required. These may be achieved through several drivers such as reduction of investment costs, reduced operation and maintenance costs, reduction of capital costs, and by increasing the energy generated during the system lifetime by means of increased efficiency or lifetime extension.

When considering PV plant lifetime and reliability, the power converter element is responsible for approximately 50 % of total failures on a solar PV plant,^[2] entailing a 60 % of the unscheduled maintenance costs.^[3] In addition, the typical expected lifetime of PV plant inverters (from string based to central configurations) is less than 15 years, thus requiring at least one full replacement when considering a typical PV-plant expected lifetime of 25 years.^[4] Thus, it is clear that there is the need to reduce the impact of failures on the inverter as well increase its lifetime to be in par with the other components. Electrolytic capacitors and power semiconductor switching devices are the weakest elements of power conversion systems, accounting for a 95 % of the power converter failures. Electrolytic capacitor failure rate can be reduced by allowing for large design margins in terms of voltage, ripple current, and temperature.^[5, 6] Power switch failures are generally classified into open-circuit fault (OCF) and short-circuit fault (SCF). The impact of the power switch failures in the inverter reliability can be reduced by adopting fault-tolerant inverter structures. These strategies are based on hardware redundancy and associated controls. In power converters, redundancy can be classified as system level, leg level, module level, and switch level.^[7] System-level redundancy allows for a simple fault-tolerant system, but at the expense of an elevated cost and reduced reliability gain. Module-level and switch-level redundancies offer a high increase on the system reliability, at the expense of an increased complexity and cost. Leg-level redundancy offers an optimum trade off between cost, performance, and reliability.^[7] Fault-tolerant in-

verters featuring leg redundancy have been largely proposed in the literature,^[7, 8, 9, 10] similar to leg-redundant fault-tolerant dc-dc converter topologies.^[11, 12] Fault detection and identification for both dc-dc and dc-ac converters has been proposed,^[13] but without fault-tolerant operation.

This paper presents a modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter based on the solution proposed on.^[14] It is composed of a modular dc-dc stage and a three-phase dc-ac stage. Modularity enables easy scalability of the inverter power rating. On the other hand, the leg-level fault-tolerant capability allows the inverter to survive a fault in the power switches on any of the converter stages. In addition, the paper also performs a reliability assessment generalized to any number of dc-dc modules, analyzes the system lifetime and cost, and validates the inverter feasibility through experimental tests with a laboratory prototype.

This paper is organized as follows. First, Section 2 describes the proposed modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter topology and the principle of operation of the reconfiguration strategy to achieve fault tolerance. Section 3 briefly describes the fault diagnosis algorithm. Section 4 performs the reliability assessment of the proposed inverter and compares its lifetime to conventional solutions for different modular configurations. Section 5 performs the economic impact evaluation of the proposed inverter considering its modularity and fault-tolerant capability, comparing its cost to conventional solutions. Section 6 presents simulation and experimental results for different emulated switch faults to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed inverter modularity and fault-tolerant capability. Finally, Section 7 outlines the conclusion.

2 Proposed modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter

The proposed modular two-stage fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter is shown in **Figure 1**. The inverter first stage consists of M dc-dc boost converters connected in parallel at its output. The second stage consists of a two-level three-phase dc-ac converter that transfers power from the dc link to the grid. The dc-dc boost converters allow feeding power from the

Figure 1: Proposed modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter.

PV strings to the dc-ac conversion stage at an optimal dc-link voltage (V_{dc}) value.

Modularity in the inverter is attained with the dc-dc conversion stage. Each of the M boost converters is a module that allows connecting a PV string to the system. Thus, the PV plant power can be scaled by adjusting the number of modules. The power rating of the dc-ac stage has to be adjusted according to the number of modules. This can be achieved by simply adjusting the heat extraction capabilities for the dc-ac stage semiconductors and the current rating of the filter inductors (L_f and r_f). Modularity at dc-ac-stage level has not been considered since it would lead to recirculating currents between the dc-ac modules, making the inverter control more complex, causing additional losses, and increasing the phase-currents distortion.^[15]

The proposed fault-tolerant inverter design has been developed as a trade-off of two-fold

conditions: to be able to survive a first fault and continue operation without downgrading the inverter nominal power and achieve fault tolerance on both stages of the inverter with a reduced increase on the converter cost.

Fault tolerance is obtained by means of adding leg-level redundancy to the system. This is achieved with the redundant switching leg comprised by switches S_{RH} and S_{RL} . In order to perform the reconfiguration of the system after a failure is detected, four-quadrant (4Q) switches T_m and T_k are added to the system, where $m = \{1, \dots, M\}$ and $k = \{A, B, C\}$. Fuses f_m , f_{kL} , and f_{kH} are added in series with each active switch to convert any SCF to a OCF. Thus a total of $M + 3$ 4Q switches and $M + 6$ fuses are required.

The principle of operation of the fault-tolerant converter is the following: In pre-fault condition, both the redundant leg and the 4Q switches are disabled. When a fault occurs in one of the operating switches, the fault is first isolated by the fuses in the faulty leg (in case a SCF occurs). Then the faulty leg is identified by a fault-diagnosis algorithm (presented in the coming section), and the redundant leg is connected in place of the faulty leg by enabling the corresponding 4Q switch. For instance, if a SCF occurs in S_{AH} , fuses f_{AH} and f_{AL} would be immediately blown, isolating the faulty leg. Then the faulty leg would be identified with the proper fault diagnosis algorithm, switch T_A would be enabled, and S_{AH} and S_{AL} command signals would be redirected to S_{RH} and S_{RL} , respectively. When an OCF occurs, fuse action is not required, since this type of fault inherently isolates the faulty leg.

3 Fault diagnosis

The fault-diagnosis method for the proposed inverter follows the same operation principle than existing methods in the literature,^[16] which consists on two algorithms: An algorithm for the dc-ac stage that allows detecting a switch failure in this stage and locating the failed switch, and an algorithm to detect a switch failure in each one of the boost converters in the dc-dc stage. Although these two algorithms are only valid for detecting OCFs, having fuses in series with each switch effectively converts any switch SCF into an OCF. Let us briefly detail the principle of operation of the two algorithms to aid in the interpretation of the

simulation and experimental results shown in Section 6.

3.1 Fault diagnosis on the dc-ac stage

The fault-diagnosis method for the dc-ac stage is based on the current Park vector approach.^[17] This method is able to detect and locate the fault in less than one fundamental period of the grid phase currents. Moreover, since the Park vector is obtained with the grid phase currents and these are already measured by the inverter control, no additional sensors are required to implement the fault diagnosis method.

In order to detect a fault in the dc-ac stage, first it is necessary to compute the inverter phase-currents Park-vector components (i_d and i_q) and phase angle (θ), defined as

$$i_d = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}i_A - \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}i_B - \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}i_C \quad (1)$$

$$i_q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}i_B - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}i_C \quad (2)$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{i_q}{i_d}\right), \quad (3)$$

where i_k is the instantaneous value of the phase k current.

During normal non-faulty steady-state operation, the Park vector rotates at the grid frequency (f_{ac}) with a magnitude approximately constant; i.e., θ follows a linear progression. Under a load transient, i_d and i_q magnitudes change while θ is not affected. However, when a switch OCF occurs, θ will be perturbed and will follow a non-linear progression. Therefore, let us define

$$d\theta = \left| \frac{d}{dt} |\theta| \right| \quad (4)$$

to detect a fault occurrence. In normal operation, $d\theta$ will be constant and equal to $DTC = 2\pi f_{ac}$. However, when a switch OCF occurs, $d\theta$ will eventually face a sudden reduction. Therefore, a fault will be detected when

$$d\theta < T_{d\theta} \quad (5)$$

is fulfilled, where $T_{\text{dte}} = k_{\text{dte}} \cdot DTC$ is the detection threshold value and $k_{\text{dte}} < 1$ is set by the user.

Fault location is performed by finding for each phase current the percentage of the fundamental period for which they have positive and negative values. This is accomplished by first computing

$$p = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i_k > -I_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$n = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i_k < I_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where I_0 is a threshold value to reduce the effect of current reading noise and is set to a value much smaller than the inverter rated current. Then a moving average with a time window of $1/f_{\text{ac}}$ is computed for p and n , resulting in location variables P_k and N_k , corresponding to S_{kL} and S_{kH} switches, respectively. Under normal operation, since half-wave symmetry is expected in the grid current waveforms, P_k and N_k values are close to 0.5. In case of a faulty switch, one of the P_k and N_k variables will reach a value close to 1, depending on the faulty-switch position. The faulty switch is then located if the corresponding variable exceeds threshold value (T_{loc}); i.e., S_{kH} is faulty if $N_k > T_{\text{loc}}$ and S_{kL} is faulty if $P_k > T_{\text{loc}}$, where $0.5 < T_{\text{loc}} < 1$.

3.2 Fault diagnosis on the dc-dc stage

The fault-diagnosis method for the dc-dc stage is independent for each boost converter and no location algorithm is required. This method is based on the boost inductor current (i_{Lm}), which is already sensed for control purpose. Therefore, the proposed solution does not add any additional cost.

The principle of operation of the fault-diagnosis method consists on comparing each i_{Lm} to threshold value $I_{Lm,\text{th}}$. If $i_{Lm} < I_{Lm,\text{th}}$ for a number of converter switching periods ($n_{T_{\text{sdc},m}}$) greater than threshold value $N_{T_{\text{sdc}}}$, switch OCF on boost converter m is detected. Threshold

value $I_{Lm,th}$ is set much smaller than the boost converter rated input current.

4 Reliability Assessment

This section analyzes the reliability of the proposed modular PV multistring inverter for three different configurations of the dc-dc stage. For instance, it is considered one, two, and three PV strings, each one connected to a dc-dc converter module; i.e., $M = \{1, 2, 3\}$. For the reliability assessment a Markov chain reliability model is adopted, since it is an effective approach which can cover many features of redundant systems such as sequence of failures, failure coverage, and state-dependent failure rates.^[18]

4.1 Assumptions

The following assumptions are considered for the reliability assessment:

- For the sake of simplicity, let us disregard degraded mode of operation; i.e., if one of the boost modules fails after the reconfiguration, the inverter will cease its operation. Moreover, let us also disregard the reparation of the inverter once a failure leads to an operation halt.
- Switches S_m , S_{kH} , S_{kL} , S_{RH} , and S_{RL} , $\forall m, k$ are implemented with insulated-gate bipolar transistoris (IGBTs).
- Reconfiguration switches T_m and T_k , $\forall m, k$ are implemented with triode thyristors (TRIACs).
- The considered system parameters are shown in Table 1.
- The selected components that compose each passive and active element shown in Figure 1 are presented in Table 2. It also features the component references, the number of components for each element, and the total number of components in the system.
- The phase legs in the dc-dc stage, dc-ac stage, and the redundant leg are implemented with power modules featuring a two-level switching leg with the IGBT-diode

pair SKM50GB12T4.

- A failure in a diode causes the same type of fault in its corresponding IGBT, since both are integrated in the same package. Thus, a failure caused by a diode fault is detected by the fault-diagnosis algorithms.
- The IGBT modules are mounted in individual heatsinks while the TRIACs are mounted together in a single heatsink. The considered heatsink thermal-resistance values for each number of modules are shown in Table 3.
- Table 4 presents the junction temperature of the semiconductor components. The operating temperature of the capacitors is 60 °C. The hotspot temperature of the boost inductors and output filter inductors is 90 °C and 70 °C, respectively. These values are computed according to the system parameters and operating conditions described in Table 1, the power losses model of the inverter, and the thermal resistance values obtained from the component manufacturers. An ambient temperature of 40 °C is considered as a worst-case scenario.

Table 1: Parameters of the proposed system on the reliability assessment.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
dc-dc module rated power	5 kW	$C_{LF,inm}, \forall m$	500 μ F
dc-ac stage rated power	5M kW	$C_{LF,outm}, \forall m$	500 μ F
$V_{pvm}, \forall m$	660 V	$C_{LF,dcm}, \forall m$	1500 μ F
Grid line-to-line rms voltage	400 V	$C_{HF,inm}, \forall m$	100 μ F
Grid power factor	1	$C_{HF,outm}, \forall m$	200 μ F
V_{dc}	800 V	$C_{HF,dcm}, \forall m$	400 μ F
dc-dc stage switching frequency	10 kHz	$L_m, \forall m$	2.5 mH
dc-ac stage switching frequency	10 kHz	L_f	588 μ H
f_{ac}	50 Hz	r_f	50 m Ω

Table 2: References and number of components

Element	Component reference	Comments	# of components per element	# of components on the system
$C_{LF,inm}$	ALC70C102FP500	Two in series.	2	$2M$
$C_{LF,outm}$	"	Two in series.	2	$2M$
$C_{LF,dc}$	"	Three strings in parallel. Two capacitors in series per string.	6	6
$C_{HF,inm}$	MKP1848C71010JY5	-	1	M
$C_{HF,outm}$	"	Two in parallel.	2	$2M$
$C_{HF,dc}$	"	Four in parallel	4	4
L_m	195E50	-	1	M
L_f	RTLX50	One inductor per phase	3	3
IGBTs + diodes (dc-dc stage)	SKM50GB12T4	-	1 + 2	$M + 2M$
IGBTs + diodes (dc-ac stage)	"	-	6 + 6	6 + 6
IGBTs + diodes (redundant leg)	"	-	2 + 2	2 + 2
TRIACs	SK45UT	-	-	3 + M

Table 3: Heatsink-thermal-resistance values ($R_{th,h-a}$) for each configuration with M modules.

Heatsink placement	M	1	2	3
Switching legs in the dc-dc stage	$R_{th,h-a}$ [KW^{-1}]	1.2	1.2	1.2
Switching legs in the dc-ac stage		1	0.5	0.25
Redundant leg		1	0.5	0.25
TRIACs		5.9	3.3	2

4.2 Component failure rates

To define the Markov-chain reliability model it is necessary to obtain the failure rates of the different components of the system at the specified working conditions. To procure such values, let us employ standardization handbook MIL-HDBK-217F,^[19] commonly used for this purpose.

Table 5 presents the values for the component failure rates (λ variables) of the relevant system elements, whose units are in failures in time (FIT); i.e., failures per 10^6 hours. These values have been computed according to the operating conditions defined in Table 1 and 4. The failure rate value for the IGBTs, diodes, and TRIACS is dependent on the number of dc-

Table 4: Semiconductor component junction temperatures (JTs) for each configuration with M modules.

M	1	2	3	Units	Description
$T_{S,dc,M}$	120	120	120	[°C]	dc-dc stage IGBTs JT
$T_{S,ac,M}$	129	129	129	"	dc-ac stage IGBTs JT
$T_{SR,dc,M}$	105	77	66	"	redundant-leg IGBTs JT when connected to the dc-dc stage
$T_{SR,ac,M}$	129	129	129	"	redundant-leg IGBTs JT when connected to the dc-ac stage
$T_{D,dc,M}$	119	119	119	"	dc-dc stage diodes JT
$T_{D,ac,M}$	120	116	113	"	dc-ac stage diodes JT
$T_{DR,dc,M}$	104	75	64	"	redundant-leg diodes JT when connected to the dc-dc stage
$T_{DR,ac,M}$	120	116	113	"	redundant-leg diodes JT when connected to the dc-ac stage
$T_{T,dc,M}$	100	75	63	"	TRIAC JT when connected to the dc-dc stage
$T_{T,ac,M}$	91	100	98	"	TRIAC JT when connected to the dc-ac stage

dc modules in the system. Thus, variable M appears in the subindex of their λ variables. It should be noted that specific failure rate values for IGBTs do not appear in MIL-HDBK-217F handbook. To overcome this, the same failure-rate model defined for the power metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistor (MOSFET) will be considered, but with a failure rate half of that of the MOSFET.^[14]

4.3 Reliability model

The reliability of each one of the considered system configurations can be analyzed with the four-state Markov chain shown in **Figure 2**. The states of the Markov chain are:

- State 0: All passive and active devices are operational; redundant and connecting devices (TRIACs) are inactive.
- State 1: One IGBT or diode on the dc-dc stage has failed; the redundant leg and corresponding TRIAC are activated.
- State 2: One IGBT or diode on the dc-ac stage has failed; the redundant leg and corresponding TRIAC are activated.
- State 3: A capacitor, inductor, second IGBT, second diode, or the TRIAC activated in the previous states have failed; the system shuts down.

Table 5: Failure-rate values of the reliability-assessment relevant inverter elements.

Capacitors & inductors	Variab.	Value [FIT]	Semiconductor components	Variab.	Value [FIT]		
					$M = 1$	$M = 2$	$M = 3$
$C_{LF,inm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CLF,in}$	0.056	$S_m, \forall m$	$\lambda_{S,dc,M}$	2.29	2.29	2.29
$C_{LF,outm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CLF,out}$	0.102	$S_{kH}, S_{kL}, \forall k$	$\lambda_{S,ac,M}$	2.55	2.55	2.55
$C_{LF,dcm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CLF,dc}$	0.102	S_{RH}, S_{RL} (redundant leg connected to dc-dc stage)	$\lambda_{SR,dc,M}$	1.88	1.25	1.05
$C_{HF,inm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CHF,in}$	0.037	S_{RH}, S_{RL} (redundant leg connected to dc-ac stage)	$\lambda_{SR,ac,M}$	2.55	2.55	2.55
$C_{HF,outm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CHF,out}$	0.074	$D_m, \forall m$	$\lambda_{D,dc,M}$	0.898	0.898	0.898
$C_{HF,dcm}, \forall m$	$\lambda_{CHF,dc}$	0.074	$D_{kH}, D_{kL}, \forall k$	$\lambda_{D,ac,M}$	0.916	0.845	0.795
$L_m, \forall m$	λ_L	0.0002	D_{RH}, D_{RL} (redundant leg connected to dc-dc stage)	$\lambda_{DR,dc,M}$	0.656	0.331	0.248
L_f	λ_{Lf}	0.0002	D_{RH}, D_{RL} (redundant leg connected to dc-ac stage)	$\lambda_{DR,ac,M}$	0.916	0.845	0.795
			$T_m, \forall m$	$\lambda_{T,dc,M}$	0.313	0.173	0.126
			$T_k, \forall k$	$\lambda_{T,ac,M}$	0.255	0.313	0.299

Figure 2: Markov-chain diagram of the modular fault-tolerant inverter system with M dc-dc modules.

The probability of being in state s at time t in configuration with M dc-dc modules is denoted as $p_{s,M}(t)$. The probability of being in each state evolves over time according to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} p_{0,M}(t) \\ p_{1,M}(t) \\ p_{2,M}(t) \\ p_{3,M}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda_{01,M} - \lambda_{02,M} - \lambda_{LC,M} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda_{01,M} & -\lambda_{13,M} - \lambda_{LC,M} & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda_{02,M} & 0 & -\lambda_{23,M} - \lambda_{LC,M} & 0 \\ \lambda_{LC,M} & \lambda_{13,M} + \lambda_{LC,M} & \lambda_{23,M} + \lambda_{LC,M} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p_{0,M}(t) \\ p_{1,M}(t) \\ p_{2,M}(t) \\ p_{3,M}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\lambda_{LC,M} = 3\lambda_{Lf} + M (\lambda_L + 2\lambda_{CLF,in} + 2\lambda_{CLF,out} + \lambda_{CHF,in} + 2\lambda_{CHF,out}) + 6\lambda_{CLF,dc} + 4\lambda_{CHF,dc} \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda_{01,M} = M \cdot (\lambda_{S,dc,M} + \lambda_{D,dc,M}) \quad (10)$$

$$\lambda_{02,M} = 6 \cdot (\lambda_{S,ac,M} + \lambda_{D,ac,M}) \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda_{13,M} = (M - 1) \cdot (\lambda_{S,dc,M} + \lambda_{D,dc,M}) + \lambda_{SR,dc,M} + \lambda_{DR,dc,M} + \lambda_{02,M} + \lambda_{T,dc,M} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda_{23,M} = 4 \cdot (\lambda_{S,ac,M} + \lambda_{D,ac,M}) + 2(\lambda_{SR,ac,M} + \lambda_{DR,ac,M}) + \lambda_{01,M} + \lambda_{T,ac,M} \quad (13)$$

The reliability of the proposed configurations can be easily assessed by comparing the system mean-time to failure (MTTF) of the three fault-tolerant configurations with the MTTF of the conventional (non-fault-tolerant) inverter topology for the same three system configurations. The MTTF for each fault-tolerant configuration is given by

$$MTTF_M = \int_0^{\infty} (p_{M,0}(t) + p_{M,1}(t) + p_{M,2}(t) + p_{M,3}(t)) dt. \quad (14)$$

Computing $MTTF_M$ with Equation (14) can be a cumbersome procedure due to the calculation of the integral part. Nonetheless, an alternative method can be employed to obtain the MTTF in a more straightforward and simpler way.^[20] In this method, it is supposed that once the end state is reached, the system is immediately repaired and returned to the initial state, thus introducing a virtual transition from state 3 to 0 with an infinite repair rate. In this situation, the probability of being in each state reaches steady-state value $P_{s,M}$. As a result, the MTTF is obtained with

$$MTTF_M = \frac{1}{\lambda_{sys,M}}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\lambda_{sys,M} = \lambda_{LC,M} \cdot P_{0,M} + (\lambda_{13,M} + \lambda_{LC,M}) \cdot P_{1,M} + (\lambda_{23,M} + \lambda_{LC,M}) \cdot P_{2,M} \quad (16)$$

and the steady-state probabilities are obtained from

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{0,M} \\ P_{1,M} \\ P_{2,M} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{01,M} & -\lambda_{13,M} - \lambda_{LC,M} & 0 \\ \lambda_{02,M} & 0 & -\lambda_{23,M} - \lambda_{LC,M} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The MTTF for the conventional inverter configurations is straight forward, since its Markov-chain diagram is composed of two states. Its MTTF can be obtained with

$$MTTF_{nFT,M} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{LC,M} + \lambda_{01,M} + \lambda_{02,M}}. \quad (18)$$

4.4 Reliability assessment results

Table 6 shows the results obtained with Equation (15) and (18), together with the ratio of the MTTF of the fault-tolerant inverter to the conventional inverter. As it can be seen, thanks to the proposed fault-tolerant solution, the lifetime of the inverter can be almost doubled compared to the conventional inverter. Moreover, such improvement is independent of the number of dc-dc modules present in the system, thus making the proposed fault-tolerant modular inverter an attractive solution. It is also worth noting that the the lifetime of both fault-tolerant and conventional inverters decreases as the number of dc-dc modules increases. This is due to the increase on the number of components of the inverter and thus the increase in the probability of a component failure and the fact that system reparation or degraded-operation mode have not been considered. Nonetheless, if degraded mode of operation was considered, the MTTF of both inverters would increase as M increases thanks to the module-level redundancy of the dc-dc stage.

Table 6: Fault-tolerant and conventional inverter MTTF and MTTF ratio as a function of M .

	M	1	2	3
$MTTF_M$ [years]		8.71	7.71	6.89
$MTTF_{M,nFT}$ [years]		4.49	3.98	3.56
$MTTF_M/MTTF_{M,nFT}$		1.94	1.94	1.94

5 Economic impact evaluation and efficiency analysis

The aim of this section is to assess the economic impact and the conversion efficiency of the proposed inverter compared to the conventional non-fault-tolerant inverter.

5.1 Economic impact evaluation

For the economic impact evaluation two relevant PV-system economic indicators are considered: system cost and performance ratio. Regarding the system cost, it is acknowledged that the proposed inverter is more expensive due to the increment of required components. The semiconductor components and ancillary circuit represent around 12 % of the total cost of a conventional inverter.^[21] In addition, it is assumed that the redundant and reconfiguration switches are the elements directly affecting the fault-tolerant-inverter cost compared to the conventional inverter. This cost is proportionally estimated according to the total number of components. Table 7 shows the cost difference of the proposed inverter to the conventional inverter in two scenarios: TRIACs have no impact on the system cost (S1) and the cost of a TRIAC is 50 % the cost of an IGBT (S2).

Table 7: Cost difference of the proposed inverter to the conventional inverter under scenarios S1 and S2.

<i>M</i>	1	2	3
Cost difference (S1)	+3.42 %	+3 %	+2.64 %
Cost difference (S2)	+6.84 %	+6.72 %	+6.6 %

As it can be seen in Table 7, the cost difference is in the range of 2.6 % – 6.8 %. This range is considered to be acceptable, since a sensitivity analysis covering a wide range of costs has been provided with both scenarios. From this analysis, it can be stated that the potential cost impact of the proposed fault-tolerant solution is minimal when the provided benefits are taken into account; i.e., the extended lifetime of the inverter and the increase on the system performance ratio.

Regarding the system performance ratio, inverter failures in the conventional solution

lead to more than 35 % of power losses in PV systems and a performance ratio reduction of among 6 %.^[22, 23, 24] Thanks to the proposed fault-tolerant solution, both figures are improved by close to 50 % as the increased expected lifetime of the inverter is almost doubled, leading to a performance ratio reduction of about 3 % in all cases.

5.2 Efficiency analysis

During pre-fault operation, the proposed converter features power losses similar to the conventional structure, with a slight increase due to the losses in the fuses in series with each switch. Nonetheless, these losses can be generally neglected due to the low-ohmic value of the fuses. In post-fault operation, conduction losses also occur on the 4Q switch enabled for the reconfiguration. Considering that the reconfiguration switches and the switching-leg active switches are implemented with TRIACs and IGBTs, respectively, then it can be stated that the post-fault conduction losses on the enabled TRIAC are approximately equal to the conduction losses on the redundant switching leg. Considering a pre-fault converter efficiency of 95 % and that conduction losses account for half of the semiconductor losses, the converter efficiency would only be reduced by 0.5 % after a fault event.

6 Simulation and experimental results

This section presents the results of the simulations and experimental tests performed on the proposed modular fault-tolerant PV multistring inverter that allow demonstrating the feasibility of the fault-diagnosis methods summarized in Section 2, as well as the converter reconfiguration strategy. Simulation and experiments have been performed on the inverter configuration with two dc-dc modules ($M = 2$) and under various fault scenarios. These results are an extension of the results presented in past work,^[16] where only simulation results were presented.

For the experimental tests, a lab-scale prototype of the proposed inverter (shown in **Figure 3**) has been developed. The inverter control, fault-diagnosis algorithms, and system monitoring have been implemented on OP4510 fast-prototyping platform from OPAL-RT.

Figure 3: Lab-scale prototype of the proposed modular fault-tolerant inverter. (a) Inverter switching and redundant legs, dc-link capacitors, reconfiguration switch, and control platform. (b) dc-dc stage capacitors and inductors, grid filter inductors, electric protection breakers, dc-link discharge resistors (dc chopper), and measurement boards.

The reconfiguration switches have been implemented employing fast-acting mechanical relays for simplicity and only one relay has been implemented for prototype-cost reasons. For the simulations, the inverter has been modeled and simulated with Matlab-Simulink software. For the simulations and experimental tests, it is considered that the PV panel strings behave as a voltage source with voltage V_{pvm} . Each dc-dc stage boost converter has its own control loop, which regulates the average value of the inductor current to target value I_{Lm}^* . The dc-ac stage control loop regulates the grid currents in order to set the dc-link voltage (v_{dc}) to target value V_{dc}^* and the grid power factor to target value $\cos(\varphi^*)$. Table 8 presents the converter specifications, fault-diagnosis algorithms parameter values, and the test conditions. The response time of the relay (18 ms) has been reproduced in the simulations.

To assess the fault-diagnosis algorithms and reconfiguration strategy, OCF faults on both inverter stages are emulated by setting the affected switch in a permanent off state through its control signal. The faulty switches that the tests have been run on are S_{AH} and S_{AL} in the dc-ac stage and S_1 in the dc-dc stage.

Figure 4 shows the results for S_{AH} fault. The switch fault is triggered at $t = 0.03$ s and $\theta = 0^\circ$. On both simulation and experimental tests, the fault in the dc-ac stage is detected and located 1.6 ms and 8.2 ms after the fault is enabled, respectively. The system

Table 8: Inverter prototype specifications, fault-diagnosis algorithms parameter values, and tests conditions.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
M	2	k_{dte}	0.3
L_1, L_2	2.5 mH	I_0	0.5 A
L_f	4.6 mH	T_{loc}	0.9
r_f	351 mH	$I_{L1,\text{th}}, I_{L2,\text{th}}$	0.5 A
$C_{\text{LF},\text{in}1}, C_{\text{LF},\text{in}2}$	none	N_{TsdC}	50
$C_{\text{LF},\text{out}1}, C_{\text{LF},\text{out}2}$	500 μF	$V_{\text{pv}1}, V_{\text{pv}2}$	140 V
$C_{\text{LF},\text{dc}}$	500 μF	$V_{\text{AB},\text{rms}}$	70 V
$C_{\text{HF},\text{in}1}, C_{\text{HF},\text{in}2}$	200 μF	$\cos(\varphi^*)$	1
$C_{\text{HF},\text{out}1}, C_{\text{HF},\text{out}2}$	100 μF	I_{L1}^*, I_{L2}^*	3.6 A
$C_{\text{HF},\text{dc}}$	200 μF	V_{dc}^*	175 V

is reconfigured 28 ms after the fault. During the time lapse between the fault triggering and the inverter reconfiguration, the dc-ac stage dc-link voltage controller is able to maintain v_{dc} at an acceptable voltage range, exhibiting a slight increase, with an overshoot of 9.7% on both simulation and experimental tests. Nonetheless, an excessive dc-link voltage overshoot would be clamped by the dc chopper in the inverter prototype.

Figure 5 shows the results for S_{AL} fault, enabled at $t = 0.03$ s ($\theta = 270^\circ$). The fault is detected and located 3.3 ms and 19 ms after the fault is engaged, respectively. The system is reconfigured approximately 38 ms after the fault occurs on both simulation and experimental tests. The dc-link voltage overshoot is 9.1%, similar to the previous case.

Figure 6 shows the results for S_1 fault, enabled at $t = 0.03$ s ($\theta = 30^\circ$). The fault in the dc-dc stage is detected 5.1 ms after the fault is enabled, in the case of the simulation, and 10.4 ms for the experimental test. This discrepancy is due to the difference on the measuring sampling time on both cases. The system is reconfigured approximately 23.2 ms and 27 ms after the fault occurs on the simulation and experimental test, respectively. In this case, the dc-link voltage suffers an undershoot of 12.6%. After the inverter reconfiguration, i_{L1} features an overshoot due to the transient response of the boost controller.

On all tested scenarios, the fault is successfully detected and located, and the inverter is reconfigured. The fault-tolerant inverter is able to reach pre-fault steady-state values in less

Figure 4: System response under an OCF in switch S_{AH} . (a) Simulation results. (b) Experimental results.

than two grid fundamental periods after the fault occurs. Moreover, both simulation and experimental results are in close agreement.

7 Conclusion

This paper has proposed an innovative modular fault-tolerant converter for solar PV applications. The modular design, fault-tolerant operation, reliability assessment, economic and efficiency impact, prototype development, and validation through simulation and lab testing have been presented. The proposed design targets the best trade-off of cost increase vs. performance improvement, allowing to almost double the inverter MTTF compared to the

Figure 5: System response under an OCF in switch S_{AL} . (a) Simulation results. (b) Experimental results.

conventional solution, regardless of the number of PV strings and associated dc-dc modules. This is accomplished with a minor economic impact, which is easily counteracted by the increase of energy yielded by the system during its extended lifetime. More so, the proposed solution enables scheduled maintenance of failed inverters without loss of energy yield. Thus, it is especially interesting for floating and remote location PV systems, which are difficult to reach and that show high operating and maintenance costs and a large mean time to repair. In addition, the method to compute the MTTF of the proposed inverter has been generalized to any number modules for non-reparation and non-degraded-operation modes, entailing a valuable contribution to the field of reliability on multistring PV inverters.

Acknowledgements

Figure 6: System response under an OCF in switch S_1 . (a) Simulation results. (b) Experimental results. The oscilloscope math channel is employed to compute $i_C = -i_A - i_B$.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under SUPER PV project (grant agreement No 792245) and from AGAUR under the project CORV (with reference 2019 LLAV 00045).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Table of Contents

A modular fault-tolerant photovoltaic multistring inverter has been proposed. Its power rating can be scaled with the dc-dc module number. The inverter fault-tolerant capability enables post-fault operation and allows almost doubling the inverter lifetime compared to non-fault-tolerant solutions in non-degraded-operation mode, with a low impact on the cost increase (3 %-7 %) and an efficiency reduction of only 0.5 %.